

Auspicious Meaning for Community Souvenir Products

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Abstract—The objective of this research was to find the relationship between auspicious meaning in eastern wisdom and the interpretation as a guideline for the design and development of community souvenirs. The sample group included 400 customers in Bangkok who used to buy community souvenir products. The information was applied to design the souvenirs which were considered for the appropriateness by 5 design specialists. The data were analyzed to find frequency, percentage, and SD with the results as follows. 1) The best factor referring to the auspicious meaning is color. The application of auspicious meaning can make the value added to the product and bring the fortune to the receivers. 2) The effectiveness of the auspicious meaning integration on the design of community souvenir product was in high level. When considering in each aspect, it was found that the interpretation aspect was in high level, the congruency of the auspicious meaning and the utility of the product was in high level. The attractiveness and the good design were in very high level while the potential of the value added in the product design was in high level. The suitable application to the design of community souvenir product was in high level.

Keywords—Auspicious meaning, community products, souvenirs.

I. INTRODUCTION

EASTERN civilization and eastern wisdom have been the sources of world civilization and knowledge in every field such as Feng Shui, which is the science in choosing good location affecting the prosperous stage, health, and the happiness of living. This idea has been accepted by western countries and it can be said that Feng Shui is the integration of more than 8 branches of sciences, i.e. physics, astrology, geology, health, environment, biology, social sciences, psychology, and architecture at the maximum ratio of the integration of 2 subjects at 34.1% [5].

Eastern countries such as China and Japan apply this knowledge to increase the value of their products successfully. A good example is the design of mascot of Olympic Games 2008 in China. The host employed the main 5 colors of 5 substances, i.e. wood, fire, earth, gold, and water to give the color of the 5 Olympic loops which were blue (water), black (gold), red (fire), yellow (earth), and green (wood) [1].

In Japan, the application of auspicious meaning and belief was in a lot of souvenirs and community products which have been accepted by every tourist both eastern and western. It is a pity that in Thailand the idea of auspicious meaning

application is very little and mostly in the form of amulets and charms [1].

The application and the integration of auspicious meaning for community souvenir products should be a good strategy to attract buyers and create value of both givers and receivers. This also creates the standard of community products and their outstanding unity [3], [6].

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- 1) To investigate the relationship between auspicious meaning and the interpretation.
- 2) To use the finding as a guideline for the design and develop the community souvenir products.

III. RESEARCH PROCEDURE

A. Scope of the Study

Population of the study included the consumers in Bangkok who used to buy community souvenir products. The sample in this study included 400 customers of the mentioned group derived by accidental sampling technique at the Community Product Exhibition Fair. Data were collected during December 2012 to March 2013.

B. Research Instrument

Questionnaires were used to ask the sample group consisting of 2 parts. Part 1 was about the personal information of the informants. Part 2 was about the customers' opinions on the application of auspicious meaning for community products. An evaluation form to measure the effectiveness of the auspicious meaning for community products.

C. Data Collection

The revised questionnaires were administered to the consumers at the Community Product Exhibition Fair. The customers were asked to complete the questionnaires and return to the researcher. So, 400 sets (or 100% of the sampling group) of the questionnaires were returned completely by 5 specialists on the appropriateness of the design.

D. Data Analysis

The data were analyzed by computer program to find percentage, arithmetic mean, and SD with the 5 rating scale range below.

4.210 – 5.000	Very high
3.410 - 4.209	High
2.610 – 3.409	Moderate
1.810 – 2.609	Low
1.000 – 1.809	Very low

The interpretation of SD

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Between 0.00-0.999 refer to no significant difference
 More than 1.000 refer to significant difference.

TABLE I
 NUMBER AND PERCENTAGE OF THE INFORMANTS

Item	Content	Number	Percentage
1	Gender: Male	145	36.3
	Female	255	63.7
2	Age: Lower than 21 years	42	10.5
	21 – 30 years	58	14.5
	31 – 40 years	111	27.7
	41 – 50 years	139	34.7
3	Higher than 50 years	48	12.0
	Occupation : Student	51	12.8
	Entrepreneur	63	15.7
	Government officials	109	27.3
	Private sector employees	153	38.2
4	Others	25	6.3
	Salary : lower than1 ,0 000Baht	7	1.7
	10,000 – 20,000 Baht	56	14.0
	20,001 – 20,000 Baht	67	16.8
	30,001 – 50,000 Baht	139	34.8
5	Higher than50000	129	32.2
	Education level : Primary level	36	9.0
	Secondary level	61	15.2
	Bachelor degree	162	40.5
	Higher than Bachelor degree	142	35.5

IV. RESULTS OF THE STUDY

The information from the questionnaires can be divided into main parts; part 1- general information and part 2- the application of auspicious meaning.

Table I presented the general information of the subjects with the details as follows. Most of the subjects were male (63.7%) while the female was 36.3% with the age between 41-50 years (34.7%) followed by 31-40 years at 27.7%. Most of the informants were employees in the private sectors at 38.2%, followed by government officials at 27.3% and entrepreneur at 15.7%. They reported their salary per month at the average of 31000-50000 Baht at 34.8% followed by over 50000 Baht at 32.2%. Most of them got bachelor degree at 40.5% followed by higher than bachelor degree at 35.5% and secondary level at 15.2% respectively.

It can be seen in Table II that the country that can apply the clearest auspicious meaning to the products is China at 52.8%. The customers mentioned that the factor with the best reflecting auspicious meaning was color at 48%. They also gave the opinions that the application of auspicious meaning on the community products would influence the buying decision at 31.7%. Moreover, most of them thought that it was appropriate to apply the auspicious meaning to the products at 87.8%. The type of the products should be the souvenirs giving fortune to the receivers at 44.5% and they reported that the application of auspicious meaning on the products could increase the added value at high level at 38.5%.

Based on the findings above, the researcher designed the 5 community souvenir products as can be seen in Table III.

TABLE II
 PERCENTAGE OF THE INFORMANTS

Item	Content	Number	Percentage
1	The country with the clearest auspicious meaning application		
	China	211	52.8
	Japan	96	24.00
	Korea	8	2.00
	Thai	85	21.2
	Others please specify	--	--
2	Which factor is the best to reflect the auspicious meaning?		
	Color	192	48.0
	Pattern	72	18.0
	Appearance	65	16.2
	Shape	45	11.2
3	Texture	22	5.5
	The application of auspicious meaning with the highest influence on buying decision		
	Highest	79	19.8
	High	127	31.7
	Moderate	98	24.5
4	Low	54	13.5
	None	42	10.5
	Is it appropriate to apply the auspicious meaning in community souvenir products?		
	Yes	351	87.8
	No	49	12.2
5	In what level that the application of auspicious meaning can increase the added value?		
	Highest	92	23
	High	154	38.5
	Moderate	78	19.5
	Low	62	15.5
	None	14	3.5
6	In what way should we apply the auspicious meaning in our community products?		
	Amulets & charms	52	13
	Seasonal and greeting souvenirs	129	32.2
	Fortune souvenirs	178	44.5
	Others- specify.	41	10.3

TABLE III
 THE DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNITY SOUVENIR PRODUCTS

Former Products	The application of auspicious meaning for the community souvenir products

The design of the community products above was considered and evaluated by 5 specialists with the results in Table IV.

TABLE IV
 MEAN AND SD OF THE DESIGN EVALUATION

Content	n1	n1	n1	n1	n1	X	S.D.
1.Be able to reflect auspicious meaning of the community souvenir products	4	5	4	4	3	4.0	0.71
2.The congruency between the auspicious meaning and the utility of the products	4	4	3	4	4	3.8	0.45
3. The overall appearance and attractiveness	5	4	4	5	4	4.4	0.55
4. Value added potential to the community products	4	4	4	4	3	3.8	0.45
5. The appropriateness in application to the community products	5	4	4	4	4	4.2	0.45
X	4.40	4.20	4.00	4.20	3.6	4.0	
S.D.	0.55	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.5	0.4	

It can be seen in Table IV that the specialists rated the integration of auspicious meaning on the community products in the average of high level (4.04). The design can be able to reflect auspicious meaning of the community souvenir products at high level (4.0). The congruency between the auspicious meaning and the utility of the products is high (3.80). The overall appearance and attractiveness is very high (4.40). Value added potential to the community products is high at 3.80. The appropriateness in application to the community products is also high at 4.20.

V.CONCLUSION

The findings showed that color is the best media to reflect the auspicious meaning. This is congruent with the design of modern organization such as financial bank which creates the consumers' memory such as green color for Thai Farmers Bank, Blue for Bangkok Bank, Purple for Siam Commercial Bank, and yellow for Krungsriyudhya Bank. The choices of color reflect the auspicious meaning and the image of a certain organization [4].

China is the country which can best apply the auspicious meaning on their products. It is congruent to the basic design principle by considering the color, pattern, appearance, shape, and materials [1].

The auspicious meaning based on 5 substance principle can be compared to the theory of colors [2].

SUGGESTION OF THE STUDY

The results of this study can be used to apply on the design of community souvenir products based on auspicious meaning of eastern wisdom. Some suggestions for a more effective application are as follows.

It is difficult to study the auspicious meaning to get the deep knowledge. In the next research there should be a concentration on a certain auspicious meaning to develop the product in the in depth values.

This study investigated too many types of products. In the next study, the scope of products should be limited to reveal more details of the products.

The findings from this study can be applied to develop the products in the set or collection such as ornaments, clothes, etc.

There should be an encouragement on the market test study to see the possibility of selling the designed products.

There should be a further research to develop the potential of the entrepreneur in designing and producing the community products.

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